

Shurpu Incantation Series

also known as “Šurpu Incantation Series”

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Entry tags: Mesopotamian Religions, Religious Group, Prayer, Text, Magic, Ancient Mesopotamian Text, Near East, Polytheistic, Ritual text, Excavated text

Shurpu, the Akkadian word for “burning,” denotes a ritual series where an incantation-priest systematically manipulated and burned objects (e.g., an onion, date clusters, bed matting, goat hair, grain flour, etc.) that signified the patient’s physical ailments and their causes. The goal of the ritual was to sympathetically remove whatever was afflicting the patient. Thus, for example, the first action the text prescribes is to peel and burn an onion, thereby “peeling” the patient’s pain and sickness from them and “burning” it off. While the magical manipulation and burning of objects corresponding to the patient’s afflictions is arguably the climax of the (nearly completely preserved) canonical Shurpu series found in Assurbanipal’s library, this text—our primary source of knowledge for the ritual—is much more complex. Consisting of 9 tablets, tablets V–VI contain the incantations for the patient’s purification via ritual burning and presents these instructions as originating from the god Marduk after he took note of the afflicted patient and asked his father Ea, the god of wisdom, about the proper course of treatment. Tablet VI ends with two incantations wishing for the ritual to placate the gods and petitioning them to judge calmly and not out of anger. The source of affliction in the Shurpu series is primarily understood as retribution for some wrong the patient had committed, even if the patient did not know exactly what it was. Thus, tablet II constitutes the most comprehensive surviving Mesopotamian sin list, its length owing to the hope that the patient’s error could be found therein and remediated by being named and ritually removed by the incantation-priest. Tablet II ends with a petition to an impressive array of deities to eliminate the patient’s sin and its consequences. Tablet III petitions the god of magic, Asalluḫi, to free the patient from curses arising from a lengthy list of possibly unfulfilled oaths, curses cast on the patient by others, or harm done by numinous power invoked during oath-taking. Tablet IV further petitions Marduk, the great punisher and protector, along with a litany of other deities, to free the patient from guilt and curse—whatever might have caused the affliction—and invokes many other deities to assist in the process. Tablet VII repeats Marduk’s interaction with Ea in tablet V–VI, but this time Ea gives abbreviated instructions to purify the patient by wiping them down with flour, having the patient spit on it (presumably to transfer guilt and its consequences), reciting an incantation over it, and leaving the mixture in the floodplain so that the gods may eliminate the impurities. Tablet VIII again invokes a litany of deities, foremost Marduk, to free the patient from guilt and curse, but also mentions witchcraft, and refers to a ritual where the patient is washed and purified with water, special stones, and special plants. Tablet IX contains 13 incantations to stimulate the efficacy of different plants and water sources used in the ritual. Tablet I has not been confidently identified. All copies (most are fragmentary) of the Shurpu Series come from Neo-Assyrian period archives, although it is likely that the work was first composed, as were many works of enduring value, in Kassite Babylonia (c. 1300). Several factors mitigate against our ability to reconstruct the precise practice of the Shurpu ritual from the ancient Shurpu composition, such as differences among the tablets of Shurpu regarding the means of purification and cause of misfortune; the seeming accumulation of incantations regarding or prayers to various deities—a tendency that can be modestly confirmed by the existence of a few disjointed passages appearing in other ancient works; and the existence of a tablet from Assur that attests to a somewhat different Shurpu ritual in terms of order, content, and length. It is best, then, to see the canonical Nineveh text as a scholarly semi-anthology with an unknown, but presumably complex, relationship to actual practice.

Date Range: 1300 BCE - 610 BCE

Region: Mesopotamian cities integrated into the Neo-Assyrian empire

Region tags: Middle East, Mesopotamia

Mesopotamian cities integrated into the Neo-Assyrian empire, especially the main cities of Kalhu (Nimrud), Nineveh, and Assur, but also Babylonia and other cities in southern Mesopotamia.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Reiner, Erica. *Šurpu: A Collection of Sumerian and Akkadian Incantations*. Archiv für Orientforschung. Beiheft 11. Vienna: Institut für Orientalistik, 1958.
- Source 2: Geller, M. J. "The *Šurpu* Incantations and Lev. V.1-5." *Journal of Semitic Studies* 25, no. 2 (Fall 1980): 181-92. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jss/25.2.181>
- Source 3: Lambert, W. G. "Two Notes on *Šurpu*." *Archiv für Orientforschung* 19 (1959-1960): 122.

Notes: Reiner is the authoritative edition and translation of the Series. Lambert's publication successfully questioned her identification of tablet 1, found at Assur, as being part of the Nineveh canonical series. Geller's study is the most extensive of the *Šurpu* Series outside of Reiner's in which, among other things, he departs from her understanding of the third tablet.

- Source 1: Borger, Rykle. "*Šurpu* II, III, IV und VIII in ‚Partitur‘." Pages 15-90 in *Wisdom, Gods, and Literature: Studies in Assyriology in Honour of W. G. Lambert*. Edited by A. R. George and I. L. Finkel. Winona Lake, IN: Eisenbrauns, 2000.

Notes: Anyone dealing with the original Akkadian or Sumerian text for tablets 2-4, 8 should consult Borger, since he not only gives the original text in a Partitur format (German for "score," as opposed to Reiner's use of a critical text apparatus), which makes it easier to compare text variants across copies, but also collated additional manuscripts found in European museums that Reiner had restricted access to.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: None to date.

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: None to date.

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Impressed

- ↳ Tool for making the impression(s)
 - Other [specify]: Reed stylus on wet clay.

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Clay

- ↳ Clay object
 - Clay tablet

- ↳ Type of clay
 - Type of clay: Varies by location.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Probably, but how exactly and to what extent cannot be determined.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

- ↳ Tomb
 - No

- ↳ Cemetery
 - No

- ↳ Temple
 - Yes

↳ Shrine

– I don't know

Notes: The question boils down to whether the domestic priestly archive at Sultantepe or the palatial findspot contexts at Assur and Nineveh would have related, nearby shrines.

↳ Altar

– No

↳ Devotional marker

– I don't know

Notes: See above under 'shrines.'

↳ Cenotaph

– No

↳ Church

– No

↳ Mosque

– No

↳ Synagogue

– No

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

↳ Monument

– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

↳ Cave(s)

– No

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– Yes

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– I don't know

Notes: The tablets were found in a variety of contexts--palatial, temple, and domestic. At minimum, the Neo-Assyrian palatial and temple archival/library contexts had carved or incised iconography, especially on walls, in nearby rooms.

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-ionic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– Yes

Notes: The authors/copyists of the Nineveh canonical recension undoubtedly were supported by the palace. The same perhaps cannot be said, for example, for those responsible for the fragments found in the Sultantepe domestic archive.

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– Yes

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– I don't know

Notes: This is a complex question. The answer is "yes" for the king, who was both the head of state and head of state religion. Moreover, high-ranking priests would have operated within the royal apparatus to aid the king in governance. But the same cannot be said, for example, about the many priests who were religious leaders but had ambiguous or little standing in governance.

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– Yes

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– Yes

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– No

Notes: I understand the question to ask whether religious texts are appealed to as an authority in order to enforce observance. In that case, the answer is no. The question is quickly problematized, however, since tradition and/or past authorities were appealed to, either explicitly or implicitly, and those voices were primarily enshrined in texts.

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– No

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– I don't know

Notes: The answer is yes if incantation-priests, who would have produced and/or used the text, receiving prebends by the palace or temples counts as 'preferential economic treatment...to support the text.'

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– Yes

↳ Present full-time?

– Yes

Notes: "Full time" would most likely apply to those responsible for and/or who used copies (including the canonical Nineveh recension) patronized by the palace.

↳ Present part-time?

– I don't know

Notes: I am not aware of any evidence that incantation-priests could be part-time, but this may be due more to the nature of the evidence.

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?

– Yes

Notes: I'm not aware of any evidence suggesting anyone other than men as incantation-priests and scribes.

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?

– No

Notes: I take the question to be asking about a specific ethnicity vis-à-vis the general population of the area. There is no reason to think that the religious specialists were a different ethnicity than the general population.

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?

– Yes

↳ Is this class/caste based on a cultural status?

– Yes

↳ Is this class/caste based on socioeconomic status?

– Yes

Notes: Incantation priests were often or always employed by the palace and temples and thus would have been part of a privileged elite. However, due to the nature of the evidence, we also cannot rule out the existence of lay incantation-priests who were privately paid.

↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Our evidence points to incantation priests operating out of a fixed location, such as a temple or palace, and not as itinerant religious specialists for hire. However, due to the nature of the evidence, we cannot falsify the existence of the latter category.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy?

– Yes

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious specialists?

– Yes

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

↳ Is it orally recited?

– Yes

- ↳ Is there any particular affect of the oral recitation of the text?
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Is it read?
 - Yes

- ↳ Is there any particular affect on the reader of the text?
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?
 - Field doesn't know

Notes: The incantations were written in a scholarly, literary register of Akkadian (and some Sumerian) that would have sounded archaic and even esoteric to those living in the first millennium, thus undoubtedly inspiring awe and wonder in the listener. What other affect there may have been on the audience is uncertain.

- ↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?
 - Specify: Sympathetic magic via burning; guilt transferral via spitting; purification via wiping with flour, washing with water, and using special stones and plants. All of these actions were accompanied by incantations and prayers.

Notes: For details, see the summary introduction to the Series above.

- ↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?
 - I don't know

Notes: Shurpu appears in the itineraries for the bīt rimki and bit salā' mē rituals performed by the king, but I am unsure if there is evidence regarding the audiences of these rituals. (At least for the bīt rimki ritual, if there were others in attendance, it would have been limited to the king's inner circle, since the location of this ritual was physically closed off to non-experts.)

- ↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?
 - Yes

- ↳ On average, how many participants are present?
 - Number of participants: 2

Notes: The Series only makes reference to two people involved in the ritual: the incantation priest and the patient. Some scholars have inferred three actors--the incantation priest, the patient, and the priest's assistant--based on the appearance of two different terms for 'incantation priest,' but this is unlikely.

- ↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– Specify: From the content of the text, it seems to have taken place whenever someone fell ill and believed it to be retribution for an unknown wrong they committed.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– I don't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– I don't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Tablet 9 consists of 13 incantations, 1-4 and 6-7 of which are addressed plants that are said to cleanse and purify the mouth of humans. Similarly, the 11th is addressed to/about incense. Especially because we do not know exactly what plants certain words refer to, we cannot rule out that some of these contained intoxicants or had intoxicating properties.

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Notes: There is no evidence of material significance of the text outside of the typical associations of writing with cultural and intellectual prestige.

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

Notes: Different recensions seem to have been known at different locales, and there is no evidence this was problematic for ancient experts. However, the recension from Nineveh is the only evidence of a canonical form, i.e., having a standardized organization based on the numbering and labeling of individual tablets.

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

Notes: See above for the Nineveh recension's canonical form.

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– No

↳ Content of text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: A "ritual tablet" from Assur, erroneously published by Reiner as tablet I of the Nineveh canonical text (see Lambert), attests to at least one other form of the Shurpu ritual than that enumerated by the Nineveh text. However, as the "ritual tablet" is in abbreviated form, it is not known whether there existed a full text tightly reflective of the outline it gives, or if the ritual synopsis owes more to an order of practice that could be derived from a standard Shurpu anthology. Regardless, due to the nature of ancient scribalism, more or less different texts of the Series would have undoubtedly existed.

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– Field doesn't know

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Yes

Notes: "Canonization" has been used to refer primarily to the Nineveh recension's standardized organization based on the numbering and labeling of individual tablets. The term is also appropriate insofar as it captures the authoritative status and influence of the text. But despite the end of the second and the first millennia BCE being a period of increasing textual conservation where the text itself was becoming a voice of authority apart from imputed authorship, "canonization" in the sense of textual fixity with a definitive list of authoritative works is anachronistic.

↳ How is the authority established?

– Yes

Notes: Authority was established on the basis of the text being perceived as

ideologically and stylistically coherent with traditional Mesopotamian scholarship. Put differently, the text was deemed to fit with other core religious and literary texts that exemplified the long stream of elite Mesopotamian scribal culture. (Note that this formulation is primarily reconstructed from analysis of form and content of primary sources and not from discussions on the matter by Mesopotamian scribes themselves, of which we have no record.) Also noteworthy is that the rituals and their accompanying incantations outlined in tablets V-VII are portrayed as originating with the gods Ea and Marduk.

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The answer is possibly yes as long as "volume" is used loosely. Some form of the Shurpu ritual appears incorporated into larger rituals that are enumerated on ritual tablets such as those of the *bīt rimki* and *bit salā' mē* rituals. However, it is uncertain whether these larger rituals would have had their own unique ritual manual in which some form of the Shurpu text would have been a modest part.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– I don't know

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual manual

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– No

Notes: Marduk and Asalluḫi (who is often identified with Marduk, although it is unclear if this is so in the Shurpu series) are especially prominent in the incantations, but this is due to their roles as gods of magic instead of being in a place of prominence over the rest of the pantheon.

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Field doesn't know

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This text does not portray the gods as having foresight, but this may be due to a lack of relevance instead of the absence of the belief in it.

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Divine reward is absent from the Shurpu series, but this may be due to lack of relevance instead of the lack of a belief in it.

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– No

Notes: I understand the question to be asking whether supernatural beings communicate either verbally or via some other code (e.g., divination) with the living, in which case the answer is no. The only communication from the gods in Shurpu is through illness, which is viewed as punishment for wrongdoing.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– No

Notes: The text does not portray supernatural beings showing any kind of emotion.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– No

Notes: The text does not portray supernatural beings showing any kind of emotion.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

Notes: The text does not portray supernatural beings possessing hunger, though this may be due to lack of relevance and not the absence of a belief in it.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– No

Notes: There is fragmentary and conflicting evidence in other Mesopotamian sources regarding the divine family tree of Mesopotamian gods and goddesses. Unsurprisingly, for the most part, the same deities in these genealogies are invoked in Shurpu prayers and incantations. However, the organization of the deities invoked in Shurpu owes more, if anything, to associations between deities and particular regions or between deities and specific domains of power.

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– No

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Yes

Notes: Note that often Shamash, the sun deity who is often portrayed as a judge, and Marduk/Asalluḫi (these are often identified as the same deity, although it is difficult to know for sure whether they are in this text), the god(s) of magic and exorcism, are foregrounded in many of Shurpu's incantations due to the text's focus on sin, punishment, and magical remediation.

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

– Specify: In some of the incantations, the order of the deities arguably owes more to their associations with particular cities or geographic areas.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: Two parallel lines in tablets V/VI and VII characterize the patient's affliction as caused by demons. These references, however, are part of a short mythological narrative about Marduk receiving incantations from his father Ea, the god of wisdom, to cure the patient. Thus, these references are probably genre specific and do not constitute well-formed, operative ideas in the logic of the text at large.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular
– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?
– Yes

↳ Libations?
– No

Notes: The idea that gods expect libations does not appear in this text but is widely attested in Mesopotamia.

↳ Food?
– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?
– No

Notes: The idea that gods expect animal sacrifices does not appear in this text but is widely attested in Mesopotamia.

↳ Human sacrifice?
– No

↳ Sacred objects?

– No

Notes: The idea that gods expect to be given sacred objects does not appear in this text but is widely attested in Mesopotamia.

↳ Daily life objects?

– No

Notes: The idea that gods expect to be given daily life objects does not appear in this text but is widely attested in Mesopotamia.

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– Yes

↳ Food

– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s)

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– Yes

Notes: This text does not attest to the idea that supernatural beings care about the murder of members of other polities, but my sense is that this was generally true in ancient Mesopotamia.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– Yes

↳ Adultery

– Yes

↳ Incest

– No

↳

Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].

– No

↳

Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)

– No

↳

Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?

– No

↳

Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

Notes: Variations of lying, such as spreading gossip, being a false witness, damaging someone's reputation, etc., are the most common type of sin listed in Shurpu.

↳

Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

Notes: All of tablet 3, much of tablet 8, and sporadically throughout the other tablets, are concerned with oath-breaking. Geller thought that the many oath violations listed--most of which are very difficult to understand--reflected four types: 1) someone swears an oath to someone and breaks the oath; 2) someone else casts an oath (=curse) on someone; 3) someone swears an oath by an inanimate object instead of a deity and breaks the oath; 4) an oath-curse is brought on by violating a ban or taboo, and thus is synonymous with transgression. Reiner affirmed Geller's first type, but did not discern the second type. She understood Geller's third type as an oath that releases a "numen" inherent in the object invoked that stayed unbound and afflicted the swearer. (Contra Geller, Reiner's interpretation and his understanding are not in opposition.) Like Geller, Reiner acknowledged that the word for oath-curse used so often in Shurpu and especially tablet 3 could mean "something evil"; however, unlike Geller's fourth category, she understood these transgressions to be specific to the context of oath-swearing.

↳

Supernatural beings care about laziness

– No

↳

Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– Yes

↳

Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– I don't know

Notes: The answer is yes if "shedding his neighbor's blood" or "destroying, expelling, driving to flight...robs and incites to rob" is considered non-lethal fighting.

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– No

Notes: This text does not attest to the idea that supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders, but my sense is that this was generally true in ancient Mesopotamia.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– Yes

Notes: More specifically, the text does not attest to vandalism, but rather theft of property through the moving of boundary markers or stealing.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– Yes

Notes: The text mentions the sin of using unfair balances.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– No

Notes: This text does not attest to the idea that supernatural beings care about/expect the maintenance of the place, but this was generally true in ancient Mesopotamia if "place" refers to a sacred site.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Specify: Many of the sins enumerated in this text are difficult to disambiguate but seem to deal with oppressing those of lower social classes such as "estranging" family members from each other and holding captives or prisoners too long. Another group of sins concerns violating proper relationships in the nuclear family: respecting one's parents and older siblings; giving one's inheritance to the eldest son, etc. (Note it is possible that the filial language may not be limited to the nuclear family, but denote gender/age relationships with people in the extended family/broader community.)

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– I don't know

Notes: "Luck" is not a term/category much used by Assyriologists, but there may be approximations in Shurpu (and other Akkadian literature) to what others refer to as "luck" for other societies.

↳ Political failure?

– No

Notes: Political failure as a form of divine punishment does not appear in in this text, although it is probably due to irrelevance than the lack of the belief in it (which is well-attested in the ancient Near East).

↳ Defeat in battle?

– No

Notes: Defeat in battle as a form of divine punishment does not appear in in this text, although it is probably due to irrelevance than the lack of the belief in it (which is well-attested in the ancient Near East).

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– No

Notes: Crop failure/bad weather as a form of divine punishment does not appear in in this text, although it is probably due to irrelevance than the lack of the belief in it (which is well-attested in the ancient Near East).

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– No

Notes: Disaster on journeys as a form of divine punishment does not appear in in this text, although it is perhaps due to irrelevance than the lack of the belief in it. I am unsure whether in other ancient Near Eastern sources the gods are often credited with causing disaster on one's journey. I am inclined to think that such events were more often perceived to be the prerogative of demons/harmful spirits.

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– No

Notes: The answer is no if one considers this category as separate from illness (including cognitive impairment) that the patient experiences in the text.

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– No

Notes: The answer is no if one considers this category as separate from illness (including cognitive impairment) that the patient experiences in the text.

↳ Sickness or illness?

– Yes

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– No

Notes: Impaired reproduction as a form of divine punishment does not appear in in this

text, although it is probably due to irrelevance than the lack of the belief in it (which is well-attested in ancient Mesopotamia).

Back luck visited on descendants?

– No

Notes: Bad luck on descendants is not present in the text; I am unsure to what extent it is attested in other Mesopotamian sources. (Part of the difficulty is that "luck" is not typically used among Assyriologists, so it would depend in part on the definition.)

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: Divine reward is absent from the Shurpu series, but this may be due to lack of relevance instead of the lack of a belief in it.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Notes: They are assumed, but not prescribed.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Notes: No, or at least not beyond specific references to possible transgressions related to offerings and maintenance of a sacred space (on which, see above under "Supernatural Monitoring.")

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Notes: If the hypothesized Kassite origins of (some form of) the text are correct, then, of the terms listed above, "empire" (albeit a small empire compared to other Mesopotamian empires throughout history) is probably best. Empire is all the more fitting if the question is directed toward the Nineveh recension,

our main source.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: I am unsure whether the field knows for sure, but my assumption is that an incantation priest, like most Mesopotamian priests, was a largely hereditary position of elite status, typically employed by the palace or a temple. Thus, of the terms listed, perhaps "Segmentary Lineage" is best

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: No.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Notes: Note that although the text does not refer to or depict institutionalized care for sick people, that copies of the text have been found in palatial and temple archives suggests the possibility of these institutions as loci for sick care.

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Notes: The text does not itself restrict this, although in Mesopotamia religious professionals were one of the few groups with access to formal education.

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

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